

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AS A BASIS OF INNOVATIONS THAT IMPACT LONG-TERM ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

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Abstract

Rapid technological change, complex social problems, economic instability, and dynamic changes in competitive conditions create an environment in which industrial enterprises must constantly evaluate their performance (both financial and non-financial). Let us note that in countries with developed market economies, non-financial indicators, which are taken into account both when forming a strategy and monitoring their current activities, play a significant role in the total mass of enterprise performance indicators. The main reason for the current situation is the excessive focus of Kazakhstani enterprises only on current financial results, regardless of their development strategy and future customer expectations. However, that approach is not suitable or assessable for long term development strategy for organization in developing country. In this article the knowledge management approach is considered as a basis for innovations which should make impact for long term development strategies for organizations.

Keywords: Strategic management, organizational development, development strategy, knowledge management, innovations.

Initially, organizational leaders focused on various financial performance indicators (for example, net profit, revenue). However, these indicators were scattered. Further, managers began to pay more and more attention to the components of financial performance indicators (product cost, accounts receivable, and others). These indicators were considered as interrelated but did not consider the influence of non-financial aspects of the organization's activities [1]. With the advent of concepts for measuring achievements, many financial indicators of an organization's activities began to be considered in conjunction with non-financial aspects of its activities, which in turn led to a significant increase in the volume of information and the need for its analytical processing. The most common and universal concept for measuring achievements at the moment is the balanced scorecard, on the basis of which it is possible to formulate an organization's development strategy.

Modern market conditions require businesses to take new approaches to corporate governance, planning and control. The correct choice of one direction or another for introducing new knowledge largely determines the effectiveness of achieving the set goals. In practice, there are frequent cases when insufficient assessment of initial economic opportunities subsequently leads to the freezing of a significant number of promising innovation and investment programs and projects due to a lack of financial and economic resources for their completion. Such situations can be avoided if, at the stage of developing strategies for the practical implementation of new knowledge, unattainable projects from the position of low initial innovative activity of the enterprise are excluded from the list of alternatives being considered.

Since the late 1990s, two concepts have become widely used in economic science and practice: "knowledge-based economy" and "information-based economy." These terms were intended to outline a new

sector of the economy. At the same time, according to several scientists, many economic entities are characterized by a situation where the potential of scientific organizations is not used enough, and the products of scientific developments do not always act as competitive goods due to the disunity of science and production due to the almost universal disruption of existing ties between scientific organizations and production [2].

It is advisable to begin the process of forming strategies for the practical implementation of new knowledge in the activities of business entities with an analysis of the economic capabilities of the organization. The choice of one strategy or another determines the formation of the corresponding patent-licensing, marketing, production, sales, financial, investment, personnel, and other types of functional policies in the innovation and economic spheres of activity.

A preliminary selection of the most effective innovations can be carried out based on an assessment of innovative behavior. This approach allows the enterprise to assess the number of promising reserves that appear due to the development of innovations. Reserves as sources of economic growth and development are usually classified and differentiated according to many criteria. For example, depending on the period of their mobilization - into current and future ones, and depending on the environment of their occurrence - into external and internal. Current reserves can be mobilized in the nearest planning period, and, as a rule, they do not require significant costs for their implementation. Promising reserves, on the contrary, require significant investments since they are mainly associated with the expansion and reconstruction of production processes. Sources of external reserves can be of both macroeconomic origin (fundamental features of the state financial, tax, customs systems) and microeconomic nature (regional monetary, natural, and climatic relationships with consumers, investment, and other business conditions) [3].

The areas within which the search for internal reserves is carried out are based largely on the practice of organizing the economic activities of enterprises and are based on an analysis of the principles and results of cost management, finance, procurement, assortment, marketing, pricing, sales network, personnel, investments and innovations. In modern economic conditions, the reserves of economic development of enterprises can be activated through the following external and internal sources of generating new knowledge:

- intensification of information exchanges between the organization and the external environment and between its internal divisions and employees, including in the research field;
- more complete knowledge and multidimensional use of their scientific developments;
- used experience and hidden knowledge of personnel in scientific and technical, organizational and managerial, production, sales, research and other areas of activity;
- revision of the fundamentals of the division of labor, including the introduction of innovative production technologies, the latest technical capabilities and computer infrastructure;
- selection of effective innovative projects, entering the market with fundamentally new services and improving products that are unique in their characteristics, etc [4].

Assessing the implementation of the results of generating new knowledge at the stage of forming a strategic business policy determines potential reserves arising from the introduction of new and improving technologies, and answers questions about possible changes in the external conditions of interaction of the enterprise with competitors, consumers, strategic partners, suppliers, shareholders, and creditors in as a result of commercialization of innovations.

Furthermore, innovative ideas are presented in the form of innovative projects and assessed from the perspective of the relationship between upcoming investment costs and subsequent economic results. Assessing the effectiveness of innovative projects is a central link in the process of forming innovative development strategies.

The starting point for determining the effectiveness of investments in the development and implementation of new technologies can be an assessment of the project as a whole or its social significance. In this sequence, the assessment of new knowledge is usually used to analyze large-scale innovation projects of national importance. At the same time, depending on the goals and scale of investment, environmental, social, budgetary, and regional efficiency is calculated [5].

If new knowledge meets the criteria for commercial assessments of the effectiveness of investments, then further the processes of development and implementation of new technologies should be analyzed from the perspective of the on-farm, economic capabilities of the enterprise for their implementation. At the same time, it is necessary to quantify the costs and answer the question of whether it is possible to implement innovative goals by specific functional units at a particular enterprise, considering its individual economic development characteristics. To solve these problems, it

is proposed to use indicators of the prospects and feasibility of innovations in specific economic conditions. The final stage of calculating the effectiveness of innovative projects can be a multidimensional comparative analysis of the obtained quantitative estimates to select, on this basis, the most promising options for new technologies or improving products for financing.

A comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of expanding activities using new technologies should begin with determining the costs of innovative projects.

To carry out such a calculation, it is necessary to determine the amount of innovation costs and group them according to the corresponding expense items.

It is advisable to structure investment costs and main financial results for an innovative project taking into account the regulatory and legislative framework for conducting business activities.

All enterprise costs associated with expansion options are divided into material costs, labor costs, accrued depreciation and other costs.

As a result, the introduction of knowledge management system for organization in order to create new innovations can establish new agenda for strategic development for any organization in developing country. The classic development strategy approaches have become obsolete in unpredictable environment. Knowledge management approach assumes continuous updates of knowledge that will impact strategy of organizations.

Since knowledge management is still new concept for Kazakhstani business it will take several time in order to accomplish correct business processes for organizations to introduce knowledge management systems in organizations. For beginning Kazakhstani organizations can invite consulting or training organizations in order to outsource knowledge management processes for organizations. However, this approach could be more expensive rather than introduce R&D department, but it will definitely have impact more quickly.

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